

Research Article

A Study on the Advertisement Effectiveness with Special Reference to Amazon Great Indian Festival Offers

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Abstract

This study assesses the advertisement effectiveness of amazon great Indian festival for a company to transmit its product to the targeted customers. Television and advertising together present a lethal combination and has become an integral part of modern society. It is the most convenient route to reach their targeted consumers. Thus, television commercials are designed in such a way that to attract the customer and create an intention for buying a company's product instead of other similar products from other companies. This study aimed at finding the advertisement effectiveness of amazon great Indian festival. The present study was conducted on 120 respondents, to know the impact of the advertisement effectiveness of amazon great Indian festival on their buying behavior. The results revealed the importance of advertisement on the buying behavior of customers.

Keywords: Television advertising, purchase intention, great Indian festival

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Introduction

Television advertisements reach larger, more audiences in such a short span of time. It attracts well attention, awareness and provides general information about the brand/ products. Now a day's television is one of the strongest medium of communication which communicates the information regarding the product or service. The television is a mass media, which can influence the individual's behaviour, life style and the living standard by cultural and regional differences. Many marketers of the big multinational companies to advertise their product to the general public use. Television advertisements creates, builds and grows brands, it builds brand fame and keeps brands alive in customer's mind for such a long period. It is a powerful driver to customers when introducing a new brand or product to the market. Television advertising allows advertisers the flexibility to use various approaches/strategies and different communication modes to make their ads memorable and emotional, depending on the product or service or on their targeted audience. When comparing to other mediums, television advertising gets mass sweep audience. Television advertising has been a popular medium for large retailers from the time it began to appear in living rooms. As to admire the audience every advertiser plays a vital role in advertising with their creativity levels and which helps the small business to run effectively and helps to make on their regular customers. Television advertisements helps media buyers and sellers alike understand each advertising campaign on a deeper level, by finding where they're falling, it is easy to optimize their campaign and reach their desired goal. Television advertisement is the most influential media even there is no acting of purchase the product still remains in our consciousness.

Amazon Great Indian Festival

Amazon's Great Indian Festival will bring a large number of great deals on top-selling products. Apart from basic discounts, Amazon will also offer a number of bundled offers in the form of product exchange, payment offers, and other cashback offers on select products. Most 'steal' deals will be available for a limited period.

Objectives of the Study

- To understand the advertising strategies adopted by Amazon to promote their great Indian festival.
- To examine the different opinions, taste and preference of advertisements on various brands from the customer's side.

Review of Literature

Kazemi and Esmaeili (2010) examined the influence of advertising on consumers' brand choice with reference to chocolate industry in India. The findings represent those advertisements are the major source of awareness of Cadbury Dairy Milk, while TV is the most effective medium. The study, through the survey of 538 randomly selected consumers of Pune, examined the role played by media on consumer brand choice of Cadbury Dairy Milk (chocolate brand). Results revealed that 37.7% of the consumers prefer Cadbury Dairy Milk more than other brands of chocolate and advertisement (52.6%) is the major cause for this brand preference. TV advertising was most preferred by 78.8% of the respondents of all the media used.

Singh (2012) on the impact of advertisement on the brand preference of aerated drinks revealed that there was an effect of the advertisements on the consumers as to the choice of their brand. According to the study, for instance, there was a significant relationship between advertisements and the choice of the brand. It also suggests that the most preferable medium of advertisements is television followed by internet and outdoor media. In addition, newspapers and radio have low rating as compared to other media. There is immense impact of advertisements on consumers as 83% respondents said that can recall the advertisements of the brands they prefer. This recall helps them in decision making while making a purchase. Gathering experience from the study the researcher opined that advertising is an important aspect of the companies to promote their product, and generate sales. Likewise, it is also important for the companies to know whether their advertisements are

effective or not concerning purchasing behavior of consumers.

Michael (2012) critically analyzed the impact of media on consumers' brand preference regarding carbonated beverage market. The data collected through the survey shows that brand preference exists in the carbonated beverage market and the media efforts affect consumer preferences and their brand choice. Out of eight different carbonated beverage brands which included in the study, Coca-Cola ranked the top position as preferred brand in carbonated beverage industry. According to this study, advertisement and taste are the major factors resulting in the success of Coca Cola. It is evident that advertisement is the major source of awareness of Coca-Cola and television is the

most effective medium as cited by most of the respondents.

Research Methodology

The present study was conducted among customers in the age group of 20 -32. A sample of certain respondents was selected for the study. A self-designed questionnaire was used for collecting the responses of the customers to identify the influence of TV Advertisements. Along with the usual statistical tools such as tables and percentage method were used for analyzing the data and arriving at the conclusion.

Gender * Satisfied by the offers provided by Amazon Great Indian Festival Crosstabulation

		Satisfied by the offers provided by Amazon Great Indian Festival					Total
		Strongly agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	
Gender	Male	13	10	10	2	2	37
	Female	50	19	8	4	2	83
Total		63	29	18	6	4	120

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	9.119 ^a	4	.058
Likelihood Ratio	8.842	4	.065
Linear-by-Linear Association	6.148	1	.013
N of Valid Cases	120		

a. 4 cells (40.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 1.23.

Findings & Suggestions

The findings depict positive impact of TV advertisement on customers' attention to advertisement of products/ services, informing about a particular brand, selecting and afterwards purchasing a brand product and changing previous brand after being informed of a new brand. As a decision-making member, as regards purchasing and consumption, women consumers are also exposed to television viewing. It is likely that advertisements have the tendency of influencing on consumer behaviour.

Conclusion and Scope for Future Research

Advertising plays a very important role in society, particularly in developed countries that have well developed mass communication infrastructures. The study provides interesting findings through correlation analysis. As people from different ages and professions including young group tend to be ardent

users of new and social media, marketing efforts through advertising in these newer forms of media should be directed at future research. Moreover, a comparison of adverts effectiveness between different media remains largely under investigated and under exploited. In addition, research should focus on examining the nature and content of advertising that may involve issues of ethics, consumers taste and preference. The study can be further extended to identify the influence of advertisement on various stages of the purchase decision which includes prepurchase, evaluation of alternatives, purchase and repurchase of the product.

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